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Report on the literature search and climate suitability analysis of *Phlyctinus callosus*

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Abstract

Climate suitability analysis allows to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest. This analysis is typically based on pest ecophysiology and/or distribution according to the different methodology/models available. In the context of the related EFSA pest risk assessment, a systematic literature search and climate suitability analysis was performed for *Phlyctinus callosus*. The current report includes the result of the systematic literature search conducted to retrieve data and information available in the scientific literature, the description of the methodology and results of the climate suitability analysis, and the list of the files published in the Zenodo including all the collected data: (i) an excel file including metadata on the literature analysed, (ii) an excel file including the observed distribution of the pest, (iii) maps related to the climate suitability analysis of *P. callosus*, (iv) a Geopackage file including the layers related to the climate suitability analysis, and (v) a zip folder containing the QGIS styles used to build the maps.

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Keywords: (climate suitability, pest risk assessment, pest distribution, *Phlyctinus callosus*, banded fruit weevil, garden weevil)

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1 Introduction

Climate suitability analysis allows risk assessors to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of an organism (IPPC, 2013). This analysis is typically based on the biology and/or distribution of the organism according to the different methodology/models available (Devorshak, 2012). A systematic literature research, in accordance with EFSA systematic review methodology (EFSA, 2010), was performed to gather relevant information on the distribution, physiology, ecology, hosts, pest biology, control methods, pest spread, and/or impact of *Phlyctinus callosus*. The data extracted from the literature search were used to analyse the climate suitability of *P. callosus* in the EU.

2 Note on this report

This document includes a description of the methodology and results of the systematic literature search and climate suitability analysis developed in the context of the EFSA Scientific Opinion on *P. callosus* for the European Union (EFSA Plant Health Panel et al., 2024). For a complete discussion of results and conclusions of the present analysis, please refer to the related Scientific Opinion.

3 Methods

3.1 Systematic literature search

Literature search was performed to capture the existing literature on *P. callosus*. The Web of Science (All Databases) and Scopus literature databases were queried, and search results were crosschecked (and integrated if needed) with records from EPPO Global database and CABI. Only the scientific and common names of the pest, retrieved from the EPPO GD¹, CABI², and CABI Thesaurus³ (Table 1) were used to develop the search string (Table 2). No other keywords were used (e.g., “biology”, “physiology”, “temperature”, “distribution”, etc...) not to limit the retrieval of documents useful for the purposes of this search.

Table 1. Scientific and common names, taxonomy, EPPO code, and main hosts of *Phlyctinus callosus*.

Scientific name	<i>Phlyctinus callosus</i>
Other scientific names	<i>Ocynoma rhyssa</i> (Olliff) <i>Peritelus (Phlyctinus) callosus</i> (Schoenherr) <i>Rhyncogonus germanus</i> (Broun) <i>Sciobius subnodosus</i> (Wollaston)
International common names	garden weevil (English) vine calandra (English) banded fruit weevil (English (ZA)) kalander v-back snoutbeetle grapevine beetle banded snout beetle

¹ <https://gd.eppo.int/>

² <https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/>

³ <https://www.cabi.org/cabithesaurus/mtwdk.exe?yi=home>

Taxonomy	garden weevil grapevine weevil Kingdom: <i>Animalia</i> Phylum: <i>Arthropoda</i> Subphylum: <i>Hexapoda</i> Class: <i>Insecta</i> Order: <i>Coleoptera</i> Family: <i>Curculionidae</i> Genus: <i>Phlyctinus</i> Species: <i>Phlyctinus callosus</i>
EPPO code	PHLYCA

Table 2. Search string queries and results from Web of Science and Scopus.

Platform	Date of search	Query	N of documents
Web of Science	15/05/2023	TS=("Phlyctinus callosus" OR "Ocynoma rhyssa" OR "Peritelus callosus" OR "Rhyncogonus germanus" OR "Sciobius subnodosus" OR "garden weevil" OR "vine calandra" OR "banded fruit weevil" OR "kalander" OR "v-back snoutbeetle" OR "banded fruit weevil" OR "banded snout beetle" OR "garden weevil" OR "grapevine beetle" OR "Rhyncogonus germanus" OR "vine calandra" OR "vine snout beetle")	102
Scopus	06/02/2023	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Phlyctinus callosus" OR "Ocynoma rhyssa" OR "Peritelus callosus" OR "Rhyncogonus germanus" OR "Sciobius subnodosus" OR "garden weevil" OR "vine calandra" OR "banded fruit weevil" OR "kalander" OR "v-back snoutbeetle" OR "banded fruit weevil" OR "banded snout beetle" OR "garden weevil" OR "grapevine beetle" OR "Rhyncogonus germanus" OR "vine calandra" OR "vine snout beetle")	54

All the references were exported to the reference manager software EndNoteX9 (The EndNote Team, 2013) and checked for duplicates.

3.2 Document screening and data extraction

Document screening was performed using the software DistillerSR (Evidence Partners, 2022) and followed a two-step approach: Title and Abstract (TIAB), and Full Text screening. In both steps the documents were screened answering the question "Is this reference relevant for the QPRA?". The first step was based on the title and abstract and the above question was applied to discriminate between relevant, irrelevant, and unclear references. A reference was considered relevant if it contained information on Pest Distribution, Physiology-Ecology, Hosts, Pest Biology, Control Methods, Pest Spread, and/or its Impact. By selecting the answer "Yes" (Figure 1), the reference was automatically moved to the next screening level (i.e., full text). When from the abstract it was unclear whether information of interest was available from the title and the abstract the "Unclear" option was selected, automatically carrying the paper on to the next step. The second step of the screening was based on the full text of the documents that passed the first step and an ad hoc questionnaire, divided in seven sections (Distribution, Physiology-Ecology, Hosts, Pest Biology, Control Methods, Spread, and Impact) was used to facilitate the extraction of data and information.

Reference Details

RefID: 2172, Trunk barriers provide effective control of banded fruit-weevil on apples and nectarines
Barnes, B. N., Knipe, M. C., Calitz, F. J.

Attachments
PDF - 2172_Barnes_Trunk barriers provide effective control of banded fruit-weevil on apples and nectarines.pdf (Standard Version) | (Annotatable Version)

Full Text Links
DOI.org

Reference Label(s):
P_callosus

No abstract uploaded

Submit Save All

1. Is this reference relevant for the QPRA?
Yes No Unclear

Figure 1. Title and Abstract Screening, Screenshot from DistillerSR (DistillerSR. Version 2.43. Evidence Partners; 2021. Accessed Jan 2023 – May 2024. <https://www.evidencepartners.com>).

Data extraction was also performed in DistillerSR for the documents passing the full-text screening.

Table 3: Information extracted from the documents and collected in the master file.

Field name	Description	Type
<i>Refid</i>	Record ID. The Refid number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller	Integer
<i>Reference</i>	Full reference for the record	String
<i>Source type</i>	Categorises the type of reference. Available options: original study, review study, distribution map, other	String
<i>Distribution</i>	Presence of information on distribution (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Physiology_Ecology</i>	Presence of information on physiology and/or ecology (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>T</i>	Presence of information on temperature (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>RH</i>	Presence of information on humidity or moisture (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Photoperiod</i>	Presence of information on photoperiod (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Host</i>	Presence of information on host availability (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Biology</i>	Presence of information on pest biology (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Impact</i>	Presence of information on the impact of the pest (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Spread</i>	Presence of information on the spread of the pest (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Control Methods</i>	Presence of information on control methods used against the pest (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean

A Master File was developed containing a summary of the information contained in each reference. Seven independent tables on each of the topics relevant for the QPRA were developed: Pest Distribution, Host list, Pest Biology, Control Methods, Pest Spread, and Impact. Table 3 includes an explanation of the fields present in each of the independent tables.

3.3 Data analysis

3.3.1 Köppen–Geiger climate classification analysis

The SCAN-Clim tool (European Food Safety Authority & Maiorano, 2022) was used to develop climate suitability maps based on the climate classification approach. The Köppen–Geiger climate classification from Kotttek et al. (2006) after the re-analysis of Rubel et al. (2017), based on the period 1986–2010 (available at <http://koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at/present.htm>), was used. The climate types present in the observed locations of *P. callosus* were identified and mapped. Since the area of the assessment is the EU, the output maps considered only climate types that are also present in the EU. The Köppen–Geiger map was created using only point observations (identified through coordinates) as input presence data.

3.3.2 Weather data for the calculation of the climate indicators

The climate indicators used in this analysis (paragraphs 3.3.3, 3.3.4 and 3.3.5), apart from the Köppen–Geiger climate classification, were calculated using the ERA5-Land dataset downloaded from the Copernicus Climate Data Store (Muñoz Sabater, 2019) for the period 1993–2022 on a global 0.1° x 0.1° grid.

3.3.3 Hardiness zones map

The hardiness zone map is a classification based on the average minimum annual temperature. It is an indicator which has been used extensively in relation to the geographic distribution of perennial plant species (Daly et al., 2012). However, this indicator can also be useful for inferring areas where a pest could overwinter or not based on winter temperatures.

The hardiness zones map implemented for this analysis was based on the updated version of the Agricultural Research Service USDA (2023), which identifies 13 main zones, each divided into two subzones, for a total of 26 hardiness zones.

The specific point locations where *P. callosus* was observed (paragraph 4.2) were used to sample the average annual minimum temperature raster layer. The sampled minimum value was used as a threshold to identify the minimum hardiness zone where the pest was observed. All the grid cells having an equal or higher hardiness zone were assumed as suitable for *P. callosus* and mapped.

3.3.4 Map with the absolute minimum soil temperature

The map of absolute minimum soil temperature shows the areas where the absolute minimum soil temperature is equal or higher than the minimum observed among the locations of pest occurrence (i.e. 0.53 °C in Te Anau, New Zealand).

3.3.5 Map with the average maximum number of days with the minimum air temperature below the lower development threshold (LDT)

The average maximum number of consecutive days below the lower development threshold was used as an indicator of climate conditions unfavourable to *P. callosus*. The LTD was calculated as described in the related EFSA Scientific Opinion (EFSA Panel on Plant Health, 2024, paragraph 3.2. *Review of pest biology*) and it corresponded to 6°C. The specific point locations were *P.*

callosus was observed (paragraph 4.2) were used to sample the raster layer of this climate indicator. The sampled maximum value for this indicator was used as a threshold and all the grid cells having an equal or lower value were mapped.

3.3.6 Geoprocessing of climate indicators and development of the scenarios

Given the different EU areas identified by the three different climatic indicators (Hardiness zones, absolute minimum soil temperature, and the average maximum number of consecutive days with the minimum air temperature below the lower development threshold), the union of the three climate indicators maps were assumed as the potential maximum area at risk (Scenario 1 - SC1). The map based on the absolute minimum soil temperature was assumed as the potential minimum area at risk (Scenario 2 - SC2).

3.3.7 Identification of suitable NUTS3 regions in the EU

The information at the grid level was summarized at NUTS3 level to identify the administrative units potentially suitable for establishment. The suitable NUTS3 regions were identified overlapping the union and absolute minimum soil temperature maps and, for each NUTS3, the percentage of area at risk of potential establishment was calculated.

4 Results

4.1 Systematic literature review

Figure 2 summarizes the results of the systematic literature search. The search in Web of Science and Scopus gathered 54 and 102 documents, respectively. A total number of 156 references were obtained. After deduplication in EndNote, 95 were imported to DistillerSR and underwent the TIAB screening. Of these, 5 references were excluded because they did not contain relevant information, and the remaining 90 were passed to the Full text screening. After the end of the TIAB screening, data extraction was performed for 98 references and additional records from GBIF about pest distribution was included. These records constituted the sources for the present analysis. In 56 of these records data on pest distribution was extracted, 58 contained details on the hosts, 16 about physio-ecology of the pest, 26 concerned its biology, 13 the impact, 2 the spread, and 39 the control methods.

Figure 2. PRISMA Diagram describing the process followed to identify, screen, and include eligible information on the distribution, hosts, physio-ecology, biology, impact, spread, and control methods for *P. callosus*.

4.2 Observed pest distribution

The literature search yielded 151 records of observation at both point locations (coordinates) and administrative unit level (Figure 3). From the observed distribution, 99 are point locations, reporting specific coordinates indicated in the paper or taken from Google Earth⁴. The remaining 52 observations are administrative units (e.g., countries, regions) identified through their FAO

⁴ <https://earth.google.com/web/>

Global Administrative Unit Layer (GAUL) codes⁵. Additional 520 occurrences from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) platform were added.

Figure 3. Known global distribution of *Phlyctinus callosus*. Red dots represent point locations, grey areas are administrative units where the pest was reported. Data extracted from the systematic literature search performed by EFSA, and from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF).

4.3 Climate indicators

4.3.1 Köppen–Geiger climate types

Among the climate types present in the EU, *P. callosus* was observed in the hot semiarid (BSh), cold semiarid (BSk), humid subtropical (Cfa), oceanic (Cfb), Mediterranean hot summer (Csa) and a Mediterranean warm summer climate (Csb) (Figure 4.).

⁵ https://developers.google.com/earthengine/datasets/catalog/FAO_GAUL_2015_level1

Figure 4. Köppen–Geiger map for *Phlyctinus callosus*.

4.3.2 Hardiness zones

The hardiness zones from 8b to 13b were observed in the locations where the pest occurs. In the EU these hardiness zones are found mainly in Ireland, Portugal (including Madeira and Açores), Spain, large part of France, the Netherlands, Belgium, Italy, Greece, Cyprus, Malta (Figure 5).

Plant Hardiness Zones for *Phlyctinus callosus*

USDA Plant Hardiness zones, highlighted in grey are the zones relevant for *Phlyctinus callosus*, and framed in black are zones present in Europe

1a (-51.1°C to -48.3°C)	4b (-31.7°C to -28.9°C)	8a (-12.2°C to -9.4°C)	11b (7.2°C to 10°C)
1b (-48.3°C to -45.6°C)	5a (-28.9°C to -26.1°C)	8b (-9.4°C to -6.7°C)	12a (10°C to 12.8°C)
2a (-45.6°C to -42.8°C)	5b (-26.1°C to -23.3°C)	9a (-6.7°C to -3.9°C)	12b (12.8°C to 15.6°C)
2b (-42.8°C to -40°C)	6a (-23.3°C to -20.6°C)	9b (-3.9°C to -1.1°C)	13a (15.6°C to 18.3°C)
3a (-40°C to -37.2°C)	6b (-20.6°C to -17.8°C)	10a (-1.1°C to 1.7°C)	13b (18.3°C to 21.1°C)
3b (-37.2°C to -34.4°C)	7a (-17.8°C to -15°C)	10b (1.7°C to 4.4°C)	
4a (-34.4°C to -31.7°C)	7b (-15°C to -12.2°C)	11a (4.4°C to 7.2°C)	

Climate data source for the period 1993-2022: Muñoz Sabater, J., (2019) was downloaded from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (2022). The results contain modified Copernicus Climate Change Service information 2020. Neither the European Commission nor ECMWF is responsible for any use that may be made of the Copernicus information or data it contains.

Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN © Eurostat
Cartography: EFSA 05/2024

Figure 5. Hardiness zone map based on the average annual minimum temperature for the period 1993-2022. The map shows the hardiness zones (highlighted in grey in the legend) above the minimum threshold where *P.callosus* was recorded and framed in black are zones present in Europe. The Hardiness zone map is based on the recent implementation of the USDA Plant Hardiness Zones (2023).

4.3.3 Average maximum number of consecutive days with the minimum air temperature below the lower development threshold

The area in the EU including a value for this indicator equal or below the number sampled in the location of observations comprises vast area of south, western, eastern, and central Europe, Cyprus, Malta, and Madeira (Figure 6.).

Figure 6. Average maximum number of consecutive days with the minimum air temperature below lower development threshold for the period 1993-2022. The map highlights the areas (in yellow) in EU where the average maximum number of consecutive days is equal or below the maximum value sampled using the *P. callosus* distribution occurrences (section 3.3.5).

4.4 Union (SC1) and Absolute minimum soil temperature (SC2) scenarios

Figure 7 shows the result of the union of the three climate indicators considered for *P. callosus*, representing the 'potential maximum suitable area'. Considering the areas covered by the single climate indicators, the union area was mainly driven by the absolute minimum soil temperature.

Figure 7. Union of Hardiness zones, absolute minimum soil temperature and the average maximum number of consecutive days with the minimum air temperature below the lower development threshold. For each indicator, only the areas relevant for *P. callosus* were considered.

Figure 8 shows absolute minimum soil temperature which is scenario 2 (SC2). In the EU, the areas with the average absolute minimum temperature higher than 0.53 °C were observed in the Republic of Ireland, Portugal, Spain, Western France, Central and South of Italy, coast of Croatia, Malta, Cyprus and Greece.

Figure 8. Absolute minimum soil temperature for the period 1993-2022. The map highlights the areas (in orange) in EU where the absolute minimum soil temperature is equal or higher than minimum value sampled using the *P. callosus* distribution occurrences (section 3.3.4).

5 Content of the *Phlyctinus callosus* Zenodo repository

Phlyctinus_callosus_Climate_Suitability_Report.pdf

The file contains the methodology and results of the Climate Suitability Analysis for *P. callosus*, describing the extensive literature search and the climate classification. The results of the databases interrogations are presented together with the process applied for documents screening and selection, summarised by a PRISMA diagram. Maps illustrate the pest distribution and the results of the climate suitability analyses. Although, we refer to the related PRA (EFSA Panel on Plant Health, 2024) for an exhaustive and detailed discussion of the results.

Phlyctinus_callosus_ANNEX_A_Master_File.csv

The file contains the list of documents selected for data extraction. The description of the fields is in *Phlyctinus_callosus_Climate_Suitability_Report.pdf* in Table 3.

Phlyctinus_callosus_ANNEX_B_Observation_File.csv

The file contains the observed distribution at a global level. Both point locations and administrative units are included.

Maps in .jpeg format

- *Phlyctinus_callosus_Distribution.jpeg*
- *Phlyctinus_callosus_KG.jpeg*
- *Phlyctinus_callosus_Areas_below_LDT.jpeg*
- *Phlyctinus_callosus_Hardiness_zones.jpeg*
- *Phlyctinus_callosus_Union_SC1.jpeg*
- *Phlyctinus_callosus_Absolute_min_soil_temp_SC2.jpeg*

Phlyctinus_callosus.gpkg

GeoPackage (.gpkg) file containing the GIS layers of the results of the analysis.

Phlyctinus_callosus_qgis_styles.zip

QGIS styles to replicate the symbology used in the maps published in the PRA. These styles were applied to the layers contained in *Phlyctinus_callosus.gpkg*

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